

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: IGBODIKA****FIRST NAME: VIRTUOUS****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

WHY STYLE IS IMPORTANT

1) INTRODUCTION

Communicating in an academic or professional manner entails following a number of style rules. These may vary depending on the country, institution and the type of document you are writing. As someone new to academic writing, I am interested in knowing why the emphasis on style, especially when I am of the opinion that what is most important is that I communicate clearly. Creative writers have similarly argued for the avoidance of following style guides, but rather every good writer should develop innate abilities to follow standard English writing styles (EUCLID 2015, 7). While these may be true, I found that following style rules are for important reasons.

For example, it is interesting to be reminded that academic writing goes beyond just communicating an idea to research, to presenting evidence based claims, find answers, and shape the belief of readers (EUCLID 2015, 2). Following certain rules, therefore, enables academic writing to achieve these. The Euclid sample response paper summarizes it by saying “Academic writing refers to a particular style of expression that researchers use to define the intellectual boundaries of their disciplines and their areas of expertise” (EUCLID 2015, 3).

This paper enumerates some of the benefits of following particular style rules in academic or professional writing. This paper adopts a very simple definition of style to mean any rule or set of rules to be followed in writing. It also refers to professional writing in some instances for the flexibility to demonstrate more examples.

2) WHY STYLE IS IMPORTANT IN WRITING

This response paper aims to establish from literature why it is necessary to follow a style in academic writing. Whether in the academia or in a professional organization, writers are often required to follow certain writing styles. It is not only important to write using particular style rules, it is equally important to be consistent with the selected style (EUCLID 2015, 7). Using our definition of style, this section examines a few benefits of following some style rules such as the use of either US or UK English, grammar, referencing, layout, use of abbreviations, structure, use of symbols etcetera (EUCLID 2015, 8).

a) It Gives Authors/Institutions an Identity

Most institutions/professions aim to establish an identity; the style of writing is commonly one of the ways this is done. A writing style is usually a critical aspect of the identity of a profession or an institution. In establishing an identity in writing, having a style of writing is not enough if it is not consistent. The consistency of writing styles in different professions also allows for different people to contribute to publications without it having the individuals personal style but rather that of the institution making it professional (EUCLID 2015, 7).

Using a particular style of writing and being consistent with it throughout your article is important in demonstrating a high level of professionalism. Rules of style in writing cover several areas such as referencing, how to treat abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, numbers, spacing, fonts and many others. However, the first level of style selection in writing I find is usually the choice to use either the US or UK writing styles. Most organizations and academic institutions recommend the use of one or the other as the approved style of writing (EUCLID 2015, 7). While a number of differences can be confusing between these two, there are more similarities than differences (EUCLID 2015, 9) which one can get use to with practice. From reading through the study materials, I realized that I have been making several mistakes where I have used these styles interchangeably in writing at my place of work despite the standard style rule prescribed. It is obvious that in academic writing, there is an even greater demand for strict adherence to style rules. The EUCLID sample response paper puts its aptly.

“Writing in academic publications is a matter of style, and is important to use the correct method adapted to readers because not all of them will agree with our claims, the aim of having an appropriate technique is to capture the ones that are prone to disagree; to do so, thought should be transformed in an accepted and trustable writing style” (EUCLID 2015, 1).

This emphasizes the important of adhering to the prescribed style of writing in academia.

b) It Makes for Easy Understanding

Writing styles would usually include the use of grammar and punctuations. Using the prescribed style of grammar and punctuation depends on if the writer is using the UK or US English. Whichever style is selected, using the right punctuation and grammar improves the reader's chances of having a clear picture of what the writer is saying. Punctuations such as commas and when to apply them can make reading either easier or difficult and can also change the meaning of a sentence. A woman, without her, man is nothing. A woman without her man, is nothing. This example is a typical case where the meaning of a sentence can be changed and/or is subject to the interpretation of the reader, by simply putting a comma before a conjunction, or by not putting it.

Grammar is a critical part of style that also helps the reader makes sense of a write up. Using the wrong tense, wrong use of “a” and “an,” wrong use of conjunctions and so on can make reading a struggle and sometimes hard to understand. Grammar and spell checks are installed in most current Microsoft word applications to help with this. After selecting the preferred English style, you can run a spelling and grammar check to correct any errors that may have been made (Cleenewerck 2019). In some rare cases, these grammar rules do not quite apply a hundred percent. A good example in the Euclid LIT review is the use of “a” and “an,” where it does not always follow to use an “a” before a consonant and an “an” before a vowel. Sometimes you just need to listen to how it reads best (EUCLID 2015, 4). A practical case of listening to hear how it sounds is ‘an Euclid Paper’ versus ‘a Euclid Paper.’

c) It Gives Credibility

Particularly in academic writing, making the effort to follow prescribed style rules in writing can give your writing credibility and a better chance of being taken seriously by other academics. This could be because a critical component of style is referencing. This means following particular rules of making reference to the work of others referred to your writing. Consistency in use of select style of referencing is also very important. In addition to giving your writing credibility, referencing guards against plagiarism, which is a serious academic offence (EUCLID 2015, n.a).

With this at the back of our minds, knowing how to refer to the work of others has its styles. Depending on a number of factors specific to the writer or institution, a suitable style of referencing should be selected. There are various styles of referencing such as the APA, Chicago, MLA and Turabian, which is the Chicago style applied to research papers (EUCLID 2015, n.a). EUCLID University recommends the use of Turabian style. Which ever it is, there is need to be consistent with that particular style of referencing throughout your writing. When referencing a piece of work, you can either make a direct quote, in which case you write verbatim what is said, you refer to the idea in your own words or you paraphrase a statement. In all cases, they will need to be referenced using the selected style of referencing. Referencing ranges from in-text referencing, footnotes, endnotes, and bibliography. Zetero may be used to insert references, although I found that difficult to do.

3) CONCLUSION

Although there are major benefits in following prescribed style rules in writing academically or professionally, mastering all the rules of style can be burdensome. I found that although the differences in the US and UK English grammar and use of punctuations can be confusing, writers will get better with practice. The inbuilt style formatting features of Microsoft word as used by EUCLID is also a helpful example for institutions to follow in order to make following style rules easier. It is also helpful to forecast enough time to editing when planning essay writing.

REFERENCES

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